

Synthesis, characterization and biological screening of some new pyridine derivatives

N. B. Patel* and S. N. Agravat

Department of Chemistry, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007, Gujarat, India

E-mail : drnavin@satyam.net.in; snagravat@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 18 August 2006, revised 26 March 2007, accepted 13 June 2007

Abstract : 2-Amino substituted benzothiazole 2_{1-12} and *p*-acetamidobenzenesulfonyl chloride **1** were used to prepare *N*⁴-(*p*-anilinosulfonamido)substitutedbenzothiazole 4_{1-12} using mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride which formed (*N*-acetyl pyridinium) an electrophilic complex which facilitated condensation to give desired product by removal of HCl. 2-[*N*⁴-(*N*²-(7-(Substitutedanilino)benzothiazolyl)sulfanilamido)amino]pyridine-3-carboxylic acid 6_{1-12} were synthesized from 2-chloropyridine-3-carboxylic acid **5** and 4_{1-12} in 2-ethoxy ethanol using Cu-powder and K_2CO_3 . 2-[*N*⁴-(*N*²-(7-Substitutedanilino)benzothiazolyl)sulfanilamido)amino]-3-[*N*¹-(4'-(2''-hydroxyethyl)piperazinyl)carbonyl]pyridine 9_{1-12} have been synthesized by the condensation of 6_{1-12} and 2-hydroxyethyl piperazine **8** for new amide derivatives via acid chloride 7_{1-12} .

Keywords : 2-Amino substituted benzothiazole, antimicrobial, electrophilic.

Pyridine derivatives are known to possess diverse biological activities such as antimicrobial¹, antiviral², anticancer³, antidepressants, anti-inflammatory and analgesic⁴. Several compounds incorporating benzothiazole moieties have been reported to possess useful antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶ and antitubercular⁷ activities. We, therefore, synthesized title compounds built upon benzothiazole skeleton incorporating sulfonamide moiety with hope of potent antimicrobial agent in a single molecular framework.

As a part of our search for biologically active compounds, we have continued our previous work on 2-chloropyridine-3-carboxylic acid⁸ with substituted benzothiazoles and piperazines. The search for new, effective and safe nuclei has led to increase their potency by molecular modifications of 2-chloropyridine-3-carboxylic acid with substituted benzothiazoles at position-2 and piperazine at position-3 of pyridine nucleus has been undertaken and reported in this paper.

The study of infrared spectrum gives us most of the required information about of certain vibrational bands or characteristic groups present in the molecule. The IR spectrum of $6_{1,3,6,10,12}$ showed characteristic bands around 3440 cm^{-1} for the N-H stretching, $3130\text{--}3070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ broad for the O-H stretching, 1698 cm^{-1} for the carbonyl group, 1450 cm^{-1} for the C-S stretching of thiazole, etc. its ¹H NMR spectrum indicated a broad singlet around at δ 13.60 ppm for the -COOH attached at position-3 of pyridine ring, a sharp singlet around at 8.55 ppm for the -SO₂NH, etc. The structures were also

proved by the MS spectrum, which gave molecular ion peak at *m/z* 517, 562, 553, 531 and 547 for $6_{1,3,6,10,12}$ respectively.

Compound 6_{1-12} on treatment with **8** via acid chloride yielded 9_{1-12} , confirmed by spectral studies. The absence of broad absorption bands for O-H stretching in IR spectrum and absence of sharp broad singlet for -COOH in ¹H NMR spectrum, which is characteristic for carboxylic acid, confirmed the new amide derivatives 9_{1-12} . In their mass spectrum, gave peak at *m/z* 629, 674, 665, 643 and 659 for $9_{1,4,7,8,12}$ corresponding to its molecular ion peak respectively. All the spectra showed a common peak at *m/z* 78 corresponding to the pyridinyl cation (mass spectral fragmentation pattern in Figs. 1 and 2).

On the basis of the structural activity relationship, observed that among the substituents present on benzothiazole ring, the chloro group plays significant role in determining the antimicrobial activity of the compounds as compare to other substituents. However, most of the compounds are moderate to less active in comparison to Ampicillin and Amphotericin-B against the same concentration.

Results and discussion

The structure activity relationship study of different pyridine derivatives has revealed that the substitution at position-3 of pyridine ring has a marked influence on antimicrobial activity. This concept inspired us to synthesized compound 9_{1-12} and screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for

Scheme

synthesized compounds was tested against gram-positive bacteria viz. *Pseudomonas sp.* and *B. subtilis* and gram-negative *Ceretium* and *E. coli* and against fungi *C. albicans* using cup-plate method (DMF as a solvent)⁹. The solution of compounds at 100 µg/ml and 200 µg/ml concentrations, were compared with standard drug Penicillin-G, Ampicillin, Amoxicillin and Amphotericin-B. The following microbial study result describe according to different functional groups attached at different positions of benzothiazole nucleus.

9_{3,9} (R = 5-NO₂, 5-CH₃) against *Pseudomonas sp.*; **9**_{4,8}

(R = 6-NO₂, 4-CH₃) against *B. subtilis*; **9**_{2,7,11} (R = 4-NO₂, 6-Cl, 4-OCH₃) against *E. coli*; **9**_{4,5,9} (R = 6-NO₂, 4-Cl, 6-Cl, 5-CH₃) against *Ceretium* displayed very good activity when compared to Penicillin-G and Amoxicillin while with Ampicillin satisfactory results were found.

9_{3,4,6} (R = 5-NO₂, 6-NO₂, 5-Cl) against *Pseudomonas sp.*; **9**₄ (R = 6-NO₂) against *B. subtilis*; **9**₇ (R = 6-Cl) against *E. coli* and **9**_{4,6} (R = 6-NO₂, 5-Cl) against *Ceretium* showed good activity at higher concentration, **9**_{3,4,6} (R = 5-NO₂, 6-NO₂, 5-Cl) against *Pseudomonas sp.*; **9**_{4,8} (R = 6-NO₂, 4-CH₃) against

Table 1. Characterization data of 6₁₋₁₂ and 9₁₋₁₂

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	% of Carbon		% of Nitrogen		% of Hydrogen	
					Found	Req.	Found	Req.	Found	Req.
6 ₁	Anilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	245	62	58.00	58.01	13.49	13.53	3.66	3.70
6 ₂	<i>o</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₆ S ₂	259	52	53.31	53.37	14.91	14.94	3.20	3.22
6 ₃	<i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₆ S ₂	191	54	53.35	53.37	14.95	14.94	3.18	3.22
6 ₄	<i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₆ S ₂	261	51	53.33	53.37	14.90	14.94	3.17	3.22
6 ₅	<i>o</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂ Cl	199	64	54.32	54.39	12.65	12.69	3.25	3.29
6 ₆	<i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂ Cl	263	60	54.37	54.39	12.64	12.69	3.27	3.29
6 ₇	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂ Cl	226	63	54.35	54.39	12.66	12.69	3.26	3.29
6 ₈	<i>o</i> -Methylanilino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	243	52	58.75	58.74	13.15	13.17	3.92	3.96
6 ₉	<i>m</i> -Methylanilino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	271	60	58.70	58.74	13.13	13.17	3.94	3.96
6 ₁₀	<i>p</i> -Methylanilino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	260	50	58.71	58.74	13.12	13.17	3.95	3.96
6 ₁₁	<i>o</i> -Methoxyanilino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅ S ₂	248	55	57.00	57.03	12.71	12.79	3.80	3.88
6 ₁₂	<i>p</i> -Methoxyanilino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅ S ₂	207	61	57.04	57.03	12.74	12.79	3.85	3.88
9 ₁	Anilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₁ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	210	63	59.08	59.10	15.54	15.56	4.92	4.96
9 ₂	<i>o</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₈ S ₂	233	60	55.15	55.20	16.58	16.62	4.45	4.49
9 ₃	<i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₈ S ₂	258	64	55.14	55.20	16.57	16.62	4.47	4.49
9 ₄	<i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₈ S ₂	239	58	55.18	55.20	16.60	16.62	4.44	4.49
9 ₅	<i>o</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂ Cl	266	60	56.00	56.05	14.71	14.77	4.51	4.55
9 ₆	<i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂ Cl	245	58	56.02	56.05	14.75	14.77	4.50	4.55
9 ₇	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂ Cl	199	64	56.04	56.05	14.73	14.77	4.53	4.55
9 ₈	<i>o</i> -Methylanilino	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	260	65	59.68	59.71	15.19	15.24	5.12	5.18
9 ₉	<i>m</i> -Methylanilino	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	256	61	59.66	59.71	15.22	15.24	5.13	5.18
9 ₁₀	<i>p</i> -Methylanilino	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	270	59	59.70	59.71	15.20	15.24	5.15	5.18
9 ₁₁	<i>o</i> -Methoxyanilino	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₅ N ₇ S ₂	229	60	58.19	58.25	14.82	14.85	5.03	5.05
9 ₁₂	<i>p</i> -Methoxyanilino	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₅ N ₇ S ₂	218	62	58.22	58.25	14.83	14.85	5.00	5.05

B. subtilis; 9_{4,6,12} (R = 6-NO₂, 5-Cl, 6-OCH₃) against *Ceretiium* and 9_{1,7,9,11} (R = -H, 6-Cl, 5-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃) against *E. coli* showed good activity at both the concentrations. All the synthesized compounds are sensitive against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

9_{1,5,12} (R = -H, 4-Cl, 6-OCH₃) displayed good antifungal activity against *C. albicans*; 9_{1,2,6,11,12} (R = -H, 4-NO₂, 5-Cl, 4-OCH₃, 6-OCH₃) showed satisfactory antifungal activity at higher concentration while others were moderate to less active. When the benzothiazole nucleus is unsubstituted or has chloro group in it, causes good inhibition of *C. albicans* at both dilutions.

Table 3 summarized the *in vitro* activity of new pyridine derivatives.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 843 spectrometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were scanned on Bruker DPX-200 FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent (chemical shift in δ ppm) and the FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon as the FAB gas. The compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. Samples were routinely purified by crystallization from ethanol : benzene (1 : 3) and checked by TLC.

Fig. 1. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of 6₃.

*N*⁴-(*p*-Acetamidosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)-benzothiazole 3₇^{6,10}: 2-Amino-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)-benzothiazole was taken in mixture of pyridine (4 ml) and acetic anhydride (20 ml). To this, *p*-acetamidobenzenesulfonylchloride 1¹¹ (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) was added and mixture was kept on a water bath for 5 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and poured in to acidic crushed ice. The solid product *N*⁴-(*p*-acetamidosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)-benzothiazole obtained was recrystallized from ethanol.

*N*⁴-(*p*-Anilinosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)-benzothiazole 4₇¹²: A mixture of *N*⁴-(*p*-acetamidosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazole 3₇ (0.015 mol) with 10% sulphuric acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was distilled and 10 ml of distillate was collected, this contains any volatile organic acids, which may be present. The residue was cooled, rendered alkaline with

20% sodium hydroxide solution, cooled and extracted with ether. Ether was distilled off to give *N*⁴-(*p*-anilinosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazole.

2-[*N*⁴-{*N*²-(7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazolyl)-sulfanilamido}amino]pyridine-3-carboxylic acid 6₇¹³: Mixture of 2-chloropyridine-3-carboxylic acid 5 (0.015 mol), *N*⁴-(*p*-anilinosulfonamido)-7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazole 4₇ (0.015 mol), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.01 mol) and copper powder (0.01 g) was refluxed in 2-ethoxyethanol (25 ml) under stirring in an oil bath at 140 °C for 5 h. The cooled mixture was diluted with water, precipitate formed was filtered and the resulted solution was acidulated to pH 5 with dil HCl when pure product precipitated. The product 2-[*N*⁴-{*N*²-(7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazolyl)sulfanilamido}amino]pyridine-3-carboxylic acid was recrystallized from absolute alcohol. Similarly, other compounds could be prepared by using same method.

Table 2. Spectral data of 6₁₋₁₂ and 9₁₋₁₂

Compd. R	IR (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR δ (ppm)	Mass (m/z)
6 ₁ Anilino	3437, 3242 (-NH str), 3171–3066 (-OH, str, br), 1699 (C=O), 1497 (C–N, C–C ring str), 1450 (thia.), 1363 (S=O, asym), 1334 (C–N str), 1176 (S=O, sym)	13.60 (1H, br s, -COOH), 10.65 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.44 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.55 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.20–6.85 (15H, m, pyridine and Ar-H)	517 (M ⁺), 499, 473, 471, 424, 241, 170, 149, 134, 122, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 51
6 ₃ <i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	3433, 3237 (-NH str), 3142–3019 (-OH, str, br), 1694 (C=O), 1487 (C–N, C–C ring str), 1450 (thia.), 1345 (S=O, asym), 1555, 1365, (NO ₂ asym, sym), 1348 (C–N str), 1161 (S=O, sym)	13.68 (1H, br s, -COOH), 10.70 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.48 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.60 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.25–6.98 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H)	562 (M ⁺), 544, 518, 516, 424, 286, 170, 149, 137, 134, 122, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 51
6 ₆ <i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	3445, 3230 (-NH str), 3130–3058 (-OH, str, br), 1696 (C=O), 1479 (C–N, C–C ring str), 1448 (thia.), 1350 (S=O, asym), 1332 (C–N str), 1162 (S=O, sym), 749 (Cl)	13.62 (1H, br s, -COOH), 10.76, (1H, s, -NH-), 9.50 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.54 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.20–6.90 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H)	553 (M ⁺), 535, 509, 507, 424, 275, 170, 149, 134, 127, 122, 112, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 51
6 ₁₀ <i>p</i> -Methylanilino	3435, 3244 (-NH str), 3137–3073 (-OH, str, br), 2974 (CH ₃), 1698 (C=O), 1485 (C–N, C–C ring str), 1451 (thia.), 1355 (S=O, asym), 1338 (C–N str), 1166 (S=O, sym)	13.66 (1H, br s, -COOH), 10.70 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.40 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.55 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.26–6.90 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 2.44 (3H, s, -CH ₃)	531 (M ⁺), 513, 487, 485, 424, 255, 170, 149, 134, 122, 108, 106, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 51
6 ₁₂ <i>p</i> -Methoxyanilino	3439, 3241 (-NH str), 3140–3033 (-OH, str, br), 1699 (C=O), 1473 (C–N, C–C ring str), 1450 (thia.), 1361 (S=O, asym), 1341 (C–N str), 1273 (OCH ₃), 1170 (S=O, sym)	13.75 (1H, br s, -COOH), 10.74 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.45 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.52 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.28–6.95 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 3.88 (3H, s, -OCH ₃)	547, (M ⁺), 529, 503, 501, 424, 271, 170, 149, 134, 122, 108, 107, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 51
9 ₁ Anilino	3425, 3290 (-NH str), 3370–3228 (-OH str, br), 2935, 2845 (C–H str), 1690 (amide-I), 1490 (C–N, C–C), 1448 (thia.), 1358 (S=O, asym), 1288 (C–N aro), 1156 (S=O, sym), 1100 (C–N ali)	10.70 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.50 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.50 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.35–6.90 (15H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 4.60 (1H, s, -OH), 3.44 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -O-), 3.18, (4H, m, pip), 2.80 (4H, m, pip), 2.20 (2H, t, >N-CH ₂ -)	629 (M ⁺), 599, 585, 558, 544, 538, 530, 503, 475, 241, 170, 149, 134, 128, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 55, 51, 45, 41, 31, 27
9 ₄ <i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	3438, 3282 (-NH str), 3368–3244 (-OH str, br), 2948, 2848 (C–H str), 1695 (amide-I), 1495 (C–N, C–C), 1452 (thia.), 1366 (S=O, asym), 1292 (C–N aro), 1164 (S=O, sym), 1098 (C–N ali)	10.74 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.46 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.60 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.30–6.88 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 4.56 (1H, s, -OH), 3.45 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -O-), 3.20 (4H, m, pip), 2.78 (4H, m, pip), 2.25 (2H, t, >N-CH ₂ -)	674 (M ⁺), 644, 630, 603, 589, 575, 548, 538, 520, 286, 170, 149, 137, 134, 128, 122, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 55, 51, 45, 41, 31, 27
9 ₇ <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	3444, 3292 (-NH str), 3380–3240 (-OH str, br), 2934, 2848 (C–H str), 1700 (amide-I), 1482 (C–N, C–C), 1454 (thia.), 1360 (S=O, asym), 1286 (C–N aro), 1154 (S=O, sym), 1092 (C–N ali)	10.80 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.55 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.54 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.30–6.78 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 4.55 (1H, s, -OH), 3.42 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -O-), 3.10 (4H, m, pip), 2.80 (4H, m, pip), 2.22 (2H, t, >N-CH ₂ -)	665 (M ⁺), 635, 621, 594, 580, 566, 539, 538, 511, 275, 170, 149, 134, 128, 127, 112, 108, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 55, 51, 45, 41, 31, 27
9 ₈ <i>o</i> -Methylanilino	3444, 3288 (-NH str), 3380–3240 (-OH str, br), 2947, 2858 (C–H str), 1705 (amide-I), 1485 (C–N, C–C), 1448 (thia.), 1354 (S=O, asym), 1290 (C–N aro), 1158 (S=O, sym), 1100 (CN ali)	10.72 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.55 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.62 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.29–6.80 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 4.62 (1H, s, -OH), 3.38 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -O-), 3.18 (4H, m, pip), 2.85 (4H, m, pip), 2.52 (3H, s, -CH ₃), 2.15 (2H, t, >N-CH ₂ -)	643 (M ⁺), 613, 599, 572, 558, 544, 538, 517, 489, 255, 170, 149, 134, 128, 108, 106, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 55, 51, 45, 41, 31, 27
9 ₁₂ <i>o</i> -Methoxyanilino	3453, 3288 (-NH str), 3365–3248 (-OH str, br), 2924, 2855 (C–H str), 1698 (amide-I), 1498 (C–N, C–C), 1450 (thia.), 1358 (S=O, asym), 1295 (C–N aro), 1160 (S=O, sym), 1108 (C–N ali)	10.84 (1H, s, -NH-), 9.56 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.58 (1H, s, -SO ₂ NH-), 8.35–6.88 (14H, m, pyridine and Ar-H), 4.66 (1H, s, -OH), 3.90 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 3.40 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -O-), 3.22 (4H, m, pip), 2.80 (4H, m, pip), 2.26 (2H, t, >N-CH ₂ -)	659 (M ⁺), 629, 615, 588, 574, 560, 538, 533, 505, 271, 170, 149, 134, 128, 122, 108, 107, 91, 90, 78, 77, 76, 55, 51, 45, 41, 31, 27

Fig. 2. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of 9₇.

Characterization and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and mass) of 6₁₋₁₂ are described in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

2-[N⁴-{N²-(7-(p-chloroanilino)benzothiazolyl)sulfanil-amido}amino]-3-[N¹-(4'-(2''-hydroxyethyl)piperaziny)-carbonyl]pyridine 9₇¹⁴ : 2-[N⁴-{N²-(7-(p-chloroanilino)-

benzothiazolyl)sulfanil-amido}amino]pyridine-3-carbonyl chloride 7₇ prepared by reported method¹⁵ was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml) and the solution was cooled in an ice bath. To the stirred solution were successively added in small portion, fresh dried pyridine (5 ml) and 2-hydroxyethylpiperazine

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity data of **9**₁₋₁₂

Compd.	Antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition in mm), 100 and 200 µg/ml								Antifungal activity (zone of inhibition in mm), 100 and 200 µg/ml <i>C. albicans</i>	
	Gram-positive				Gram-negative					
	<i>Pseudomonas</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>Ceretium</i>		<i>E. coli</i>			
9 ₁	4	7	6	7	6	8	7	10	6	10
9 ₂	5	10	3	4	6	9	8	9	4	9
9 ₃	8	11	7	10	7	10	6	9	2	5
9 ₄	6	12	9	11	9	11	–	5	–	2
9 ₅	3	7	4	6	8	9	6	7	5	7
9 ₆	6	11	2	8	7	11	5	9	4	9
9 ₇	5	8	7	9	–	3	8	11	3	6
9 ₈	2	4	8	10	6	7	5	8	3	3
9 ₉	8	9	6	9	8	9	7	10	1	2
9 ₁₀	6	7	5	7	7	9	6	9	–	4
9 ₁₁	5	10	–	3	2	4	8	10	4	8
9 ₁₂	7	8	6	9	8	10	7	12	5	9
Penicillin-G	12	21	14	25	13	22	14	25		
Ampicillin	15	28	17	30	18	31	18	30		
Amoxicillin	13	24	16	29	15	27	16	28		
Amphotericin-B									8	18

(0.01 mol) **8**. The mixture was warmed for 1.5 h at 70 °C. After the completion of reaction; the solvent was removed by vacuum distillation. The crude product 2-[N⁴-(N²-(7-(*p*-chloroanilino)benzothiazoly)sulfanilamido)amino]-3-[N¹-(4-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazinyl)carbonyl]pyridine was obtained and collected, which was recrystallized from ethanol : benzene (1 : 3). Similarly, other compounds could be prepared by using same method.

Characterization and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and mass) of **9**₁₋₁₂ are described in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head, Department of Chemistry for providing research facilities, SAIF, Chandigarh for providing spectral data and CDRI, Lucknow for elemental analysis. Authors are also thankful to the Head, Bioscience Department of VNSGU, Surat for determining the antimicrobial activity.

References

- P. D. Bouzard, P. D. Cesare, C. Dussy, J. P. Jacquet and A. Jaegly, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1992, **29**, 985.
- O. Tabarrini, G. Manfroni, A. Fravolini, V. Cecchetti, S. Stefano, E. D. Clereq, J. Rozenski, B. Canard, H. Dutarte, J. Paeshuyse and J. Neyts, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **49**, 2621.
- S. X. Cai, N. S. Jia, J. Herich, J. Guastella, S. Reddy, B. Tseng, J. Drewe and S. Kasibhatla, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 2474.
- J. A. Lowe, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **112**, 21008.
- B. M. Gurupadaiah, E. Jayachandran, B. Shivakumar, A. N. Nagappa and L. V. G. Nargund, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, **7**, 213.
- P. Gopkumar, B. Shivakumar, E. Jayachandran, A. N. Nagappa, L. V. G. Nargund and B. M. Gurupadaiah, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **11**, 39.
- B. G. Khadse and S. R. Sengupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 407.
- N. B. Patel and S. N. Agravat, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2006, **15**, 395; *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2006, **22**, 1; N. B. Patel and P. R. Bhagat, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2001, **18**, 56; *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **11**, 77.
- A. L. Barry, "The Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test; Principle and Practices", Illus lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, Pa, USA, 1976.
- S. R. Bhusare, R. P. Pawar and Y. B. Vibhute, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **11**, 79.
- A. I. Vogel, "Small Scale Preparations", CBS Publishers & Distributors, Delhi, 2nd ed., 1998, Part-I, pp. 366-367.
- A. I. Vogel, "Small Scale Preparations", CBS Publishers & Distributors, Delhi, 2nd ed., 1998, Part-II, pp. 209-210.
- J. A. Lowe III, R. L. Archer, D. S. Chapin, J. B. Cheng, D. Helweg, J. L. Johnson, B. K. Koe, L. A. Lebel, P. F. Moore, J. A. Nielsen, L. L. Russo and J. T. Shirley, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 624.
- M. Vlassa, J. Barbe and P. Brounat, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1997, **7**, 149.
- A. I. Vogel, "Small Scale Preparations", CBS Publishers & Distributors, Delhi, 2nd ed., 1998, Part-I, p. 345.